

THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT COGNITIVE ACTIVITY

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The difference between education in a higher educational institution and education in primary and secondary vocational schools is that the student rises to a new, higher level in his educational activities - the teacher's guidance and passes from studying under supervision to independent assimilation of the scientific landscape of the world, learns methods of teaching and independent learning. The success of this process depends on the level of cognitive independence of students.

In the late 1970s and early 1980s, M.I. Makhmutov and I.Ya. Lerner [1]'s books on problem-based learning, interest in the formation of students' cognitive independence has increased significantly. One of the main ideas of problem-based education related to the fact that knowledge should not be given to students in a ready-made form, but should be acquired by them "... in the process of independent cognitive activity in a problem situation" [2, p. 124-125] science and in the conditions of the rapid development of technology, it turned out to be in high demand in the training of specialists.

In the last decades of the last century, the efforts to activate the process of development of cognitive independence of higher education students were very diverse. First of all, there were various options for combining the traditional structure of this lecture with lectures and discussions [3; 4 and others]. These methods of interaction between the teacher and students are not considered as an informational monologue, but as an active dialogue with a group of interlocutors. A characteristic feature of a scientific debate, for example, different from a dispute, is that in order to clarify the truth, it is necessary to study different points of view on the problem, a dialogue is needed in which the opponents communicate, and they do not achieve verbal victory, but through the analysis and synthesis of opinions. they strive for agreement and mutual understanding.

In the period under review, it is possible to include specially organized seminars and practical training as more effective means of forming students' cognitive

independence, which are not to deliver a certain amount of educational information to students, but to arm them with reasonable methods and tools. aims. As an example, we can cite different options for implementing the method of systematic formation of mental actions and concepts in higher education (II Ilyasov, AI Podolsky, ZA Reshetova, NF Talizina, etc.). The specific features of using the method are as follows:

- some stages of mental actions and the formation of concepts can be skipped, or work on them can be significantly reduced. However, this does not apply to the formation of fundamentally new actions or skills, since the omission of stages can negatively affect the parameters of the action, such as generalization, mastery and consistency;
- realization of professional interests of students, inclusion of the formed task in the content of future professional activity is important in forming the motivation of action;
- usually, the highest types of construction of the guiding basis of action (or teaching types) are used when the student independently discovers the guiding principle. This is possible due to the high level of generalization of knowledge, skills and competences that serve the orientation process itself, as a result of which it is almost never required to build the orientation base from scratch;
- A very important part of your work in training in higher education is a meaningful analysis of the material to highlight invariants that will allow you to significantly reduce the amount of information to be learned in a certain field of knowledge [5].

country's higher educational institutions, the role of laboratory work as the most important method of independent work and scientific research during the study period of students was not only preserved, but also strengthened.

From the point of view of our research, the technologies that use computing techniques, which allow to speed up and facilitate the process of formation of cognitive independence as much as possible, are of interest. For example, the " Engineering Education " platform is being developed as a result of my research at the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology. The platform consists of forming the informational and methodological support for the development of the individual educational trajectory of future engineers, in which future engineers will increase their personal competence by collecting appropriate points for the courses. Another advantage of the platform is that it determines the level of competence of engineers. This new platform for learning gives the student the opportunity to use the following forms of education:

- ✓ teaching with a glossary, which involves independent study of the system of concepts and categories of the educational module or subject;
- ✓ algorithmic acquisition of skills based on individual learning of methods of performing actions provided by a set of methods and processes;
- ✓ *educational environment*, where virtual didactic tools are used to allow students to "immerse" in the studied material ;
- ✓ *analytical teaching* based on the presentation of historical, analytical and other materials on a specific educational module or the entire subject ;
- ✓ *developmental training* as a technological method designed to ensure independent learning and personal growth of students, readiness to solve non-standard problems and formation of other qualifications and skills ;
- ✓ *total control* of knowledge, which consists in determining the level of mastery of knowledge and mastery of skills on the entire spectrum of studied science problems [6].

Chelyabinsk State Pedagogical University professor D.Sh. Sailor; The work carried out under his leadership is also important for our research.

B. Blum, LS Vygotsky, A.Ya. Based on the work of scientists such as Lerner, NF Talizina, MA Kholodnaya in the field of formation of cognitive independence, this team developed an educational technology aimed at the intellectual development of students and schoolchildren based on the personalization of teaching. In addition to the cognitive functions (providing social experience), this technology allows to implement the psychological function (creating conditions for the formation of the inner subjective world of the individual, taking into account the uniqueness, value and unpredictability of the psychological capabilities of each student).

The total amount of independent work hours of full-time undergraduate students is about 70% of the total hours in the subject, up to half of which is allocated to independent work with the participation of the teacher. In the part-time department of education, the volume of independent work of students should be at least 80% of the total volume of allocated credits.

Through this thesis, starting the motivational mechanisms of students' cognitive independence at the initial stage of education and forming instrumental preparation for independent work on acquiring knowledge will not only ensure success in the credit education system, but also help future professionals to acquire knowledge and use it throughout their lives. allows to complete, develop, improve, self-realization.

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